

Participative Leadership Practice in Asia Context: A Literature Review

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ABSTRACT: The importance of participatory leadership practices in schools attracts researchers to research, and this article is used to test how participatory leadership practices in schools. The review process begins with a search engine, Google Scholar, to search for articles with keywords, participatory leadership. There are several articles on the review of participatory leadership practices especially in the Asian context, which can be found. The purpose of this review is to investigate participatory leadership practices at schools in the Asian context. Based on the results of literature reviews from various countries in Asia, we find that practice. Strong participatory leadership can create structures to facilitate the work of teachers by strengthening organizational belief systems and these factors together encourage student learning and leadership is carried out persuasively creating harmonious cooperation, fostering loyalty and participation of subordinates.

KEYWORDS: Application, Practice, Participatory Leadership

INTRODUCTION

In the era of the industrial revolution 4.0 change is happening so fast, transformation in the education system must be done to ensure that education in a nation seeks to provide the best education to future generations. In line with these developments, almost most countries in the world are making improvements and re-evaluating the existing education system in their countries. Therefore, the emphasis on the quality of school leaders is one of the keys to change to mobilize educational transformation (Blase & Blase, 1999). Leadership in an institution, without exception the school is important and significant in determining the effectiveness and success of the education process. The role of the principal is expected to improve teacher performance. The principal needs to improve managerial technical skills because the progress of a school cannot be separated from the role of the principal. The school principal motivates the teacher to perform well. and increasing and maintaining teacher's teaching motivation, so that teacher's motivation to teach can be improved and consistent from time to time because motivation is a driving force that creates the excitement of one's work, so they want to work together, effectively and integrated with all their efforts to achieve satisfaction (Yuneti, Hamdan, & Pranosa, 2019).

Leadership is an important force in the framework of management, therefore the ability to lead effectively is an organizational success. The principal should try to devote all of his abilities in carrying out his duties to achieve the goals of the vision and mission. The ability of a leader must be able to assess the ability of subordinates to get human resources that match their abilities. In this case the principal has a personality who becomes a role model for his subordinates in making decisions, motivating, engaging with school conditions, sealing authority and smooth communication with subordinates (Cape, 2019).

Participatory leadership is a leadership style in it shows that leaders always include subordinates in making decisions and policies related to problems faced by the company to achieve the targets set. So that it will foster cooperation a solid relationship between leaders and subordinates, so that will give a sense of trust is valued for subordinates who are part of the decision makers indirectly (Rusyidina, Dewi, & Mardiana, 2019). In addition participatory leadership is a way of leading that allows subordinates to participate in the decision making process and if the process influences the group, or the group in question is able to play a role in decision making, the supervisor not only provides opportunities for those who take the initiative, but also helps complete their tasks (Nurman, Yuliejantiningasih, & Roshayanti, 2018). In its achievement, the role is to assist and realize education in accordance with the vision and mission of the school and especially to give high motivation to teachers to improve their performance. But this should be a concern to all parties that the leader not only gives the task but also provides counseling, implementation and join with his subordinates.

Based on the results of the preliminary study, the school quality is still low, namely the low student graduation score, the ability of teachers who do not meet the competency standards, learning strategies, lack of facilities and infrastructures, which certainly requires the participation of the principal as a leader. However, it was made clear by Deming that 80% of quality problems were caused more by management, and the remaining 20% by HR (Nurman et al., 2018).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Principal's Leadership

Leadership according to Heifetz is a social activity (Aravena, 2019). The principal is the person who has the highest authority in the school because the principal is responsible for all school activities and plays an important role in improving the quality of education (Brooks & Brooks, 2019), (Truong, Hallinger, & Sanga, 2017), (Eisenschmidt, Kuusisto, Poom-Valickis, & Tirri, 2019). Leadership is a process of influencing others to behave in accordance with the wishes of the leader (Azizah, Latief, & Tumanggung, 2018). Principal's leadership involves trying to elevate people's views beyond self-interest to a joint effort, for a common goal (Winardi, Nurkolis, & Yuliejantiningasih, 2017). The function of leadership is to build organizational conditions that foster high quality teaching and produce improvements in learning outcomes (Leithwood, Harris, & Hopkins, 2019). Potential learners can be influenced by principal's leadership (Urlick, 2016). The principal acts as a central force which is the driving force of school life (Setiyati, 2014).

Three types of principals' leader's profile were identified: "profiles that think of people", "profiles of administrative minds" and "profiles of moderate minds" (Dou, Devos, & Valcke, 2017). School principals have the greatest access in the needs of district leaders, parents, community members of school staff and students (Hallinger, Walker, Nguyen, Truong, & Nguyen, 2017). The principal's job, as a school leader, is a complex and diverse effort. Recent investigations have found that principals who emphasize instructional leadership behavior have a stronger positive impact on student achievement than principals who emphasize other styles (Boyce & Bowers, 2018).

B. Participatory Leadership

Participatory Leadership, that is, if a leader in carrying out his leadership carried out persuasively creates harmonious cooperation, fostering loyalty and participation of subordinates. Participatory Leadership Style has the power to motivate subordinates, with increased work motivation and leaders carry out persuasively it will create harmonious cooperation between leaders and subordinates, foster subordinate loyalty, and most importantly be able to foster subordinate participation (Gentari & Sumiati, 2019).

This opinion is reinforced by Likert who said that the participative leadership style is a leadership style that shows that all problems that arise in the organization are solved together between leaders and subordinates. This style of trusting and paying attention to the opinions of subordinates, creating togetherness, and the existence of two-way communication. Likert concludes that participatory leadership is the most appropriate leadership style to achieve the quality of both processes and products in an organization (Hastuti, Soegito, & Roshayanti, 2017).

Participatory leadership consists of four factors: developing and maintaining relationships, obtaining and giving information, making decisions, and influencing people (Akmal Lunas, 2019). In participatory leadership, there is an exchange of ideas between leaders and followers in decision making, with the leader's role providing facilities and communication. This leadership involves the work relationship behavior of a follower making it possible to express his ideas or ideas so that they have the opportunity to realize their role in the group (Sumiarsih, 2017).

III. METHOD

This literature review focuses on participatory leadership practices in schools.

A. Search and Review Methods

The review process begins with a search engine, google scholar, to search for articles with keywords. "Participatory leadership". The search ranged from 2015-2019 and identified a total of 150 studies and articles. The criteria for inclusion in this study are as follows:

- a. Qualitative results from instructional leadership practices in schools.
- b. Research carried out in Asia.
- c. This research uses English.
- d. Dissertations and theses are excluded.

The steps in the literature review of each of the leadership and participant variables include:

Step 1: Formulate the Problem

- a. Choose a topic that fits the issue and interest.
- b. The problem must be written completely and accurately.

Step 2: Look for Literature

- a. Look for literature relevant to research.
- b. Get an overview of the research topic.
- c. Research sources are very helpful if supported by knowledge of the topic being studied.
- d. These sources provide an overview / summary of previous research.

Step 3: Evaluate Data

- a. Look at any contribution to the topic discussed.
- b. Search and find the right data source as needed to support research.
- c. Data can be in the form of qualitative data, quantitative data or data derived from a combination of both.

Step 4: Analysis and Interpretation

- a. Discuss and find and summarize literature.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table Participatory Leadership Practices in Schools

Author and Year	Title	Country	Method	Sample	Result
Felipe Aravena (2019)	Destructive Leadership Behavior: An Exploratory study In Chile	Chile	Qualitative	-	Leaders have perceptions about the leadership process.
Yuneti, Hamdan, Prannosa (2019)	Participatory Leadership and Principal Communication on Teacher Performance	Lubuk Linggau	Quantitative	53	Has the influence of participatory leadership and principal communication.
Hastuti, Soegito, Roshayanti (2017)	The Influence of Principal Participatory Leadership Styles And School Climate On Teacher's Work Ethic	Semarang	Quantitative	265	There is a positive influence on the principals' participative leadership style and school climate simultaneously on the work ethic of the State Junior High School teachers in Sub Rayon 02 Semarang City expressed by the equation $Y = 82,415 + 0.202 X_1 + 0.192 X_2$; correlation strength of 0.293 with a contribution of 0.086 or 8.6%.

Melanie C. Brooks & Jeffrey S. Brooks (2018)	Culturally (Ir) Relevant School Leadership: Ethno-Religious Conflict and School Administration in Philosophy	Australia	Qualitative	-	Principals in north ernmindanao are leaders who are not culturally relevant. They perpetuate the status quo of marginalization of students from various backgrounds. As a result, some students receive the opportunity to get a quality education while others do not.
Rusdina, Dwi, Mardiana (2019)	Influence of Participatory Leadership and the Environment Physical Work Against K Work on the Company	Banten	Quantitative	74 employees	Available positive and significant influence between the variables of partitionative leadership on performance, physical work environment on performance, and participative leadership and physical work environment simultaneously on performance.
Eve Eisenschmidt, Elina Kuusisto, Katrin Poom-Valickis & Kirsi Tirri (2019)	Virtues That Create Purpose For Ethical Leadership: Exemplary Principals From Estonia And Finland	Finland	Qualitative	-	Principals demonstrate the virtue of wisdom and knowledge in creating long-term provisions for their schools and building schools for future generations.
Winardi, Nurkolis, Yliejatningsih (2017)	The Effect of Principal Leadership and Teacher Professional Competence on Effective Schools in the State Junior High School of Rayon Patebon Kendal Regency.	Semarang	Quantitative	65	1) There is an influence on the realization of an effective school with F arithmetic (41,201) > F table (3.36) with a contribution of 35.5%, 2) There is an influence on the realization of an effective school with F arithmetic (26,654) > F table (3.36) with a contribution of 26.2%, 3) There is an influence of the principal's transformational leadership and professional competence of teachers on the realization of an effective school with the calculated F price (29.632) > F table (3.44) with a contribution of 44.5%.
Diya Dou, Geert Devos and Martin Valcke, (2016)	The Relationships Between school Autonomy Gap, Principal Leadership, Teachers' Jobs Satisfaction And	China	Quantitative	528 teachers and 59 principals and assistant principals participated	Significant instructional and transformational leadership on teacher job satisfaction and organizational commitment, mediated by the indirect impact of the school climate and teacher's self-efficacy.

	Organizational Commitment				
Lunas, Amri (2019)	The Effect of Participatory Leadership on Job Satisfaction and Respect for Employees as a Mediating Variable	Banda Aceh	Quantitative	100 nurses	a. Participatory Leadership influences Job Satisfaction, b. Participatory leadership influences respect for employees, c. Respect for Employees influences Job Satisfaction, and d. Respect for Employees mediates the effect of Participatory Leadership on Job Satisfaction.
Felipe Aravena, (2017)	Destructive Leadership Behavior: An Exploratory Study in Chile	Chile	Qualitative	-	The leader has an impact on the teacher's perception of the leadership process.
Azizah, Latief, Tumanggung (2018)	Effectiveness of Head Leadership School in Developing Literacy Culture	Tumanggung	Qualitative	-	The design the development of literacy culture in MA Aziziyah Tangerang has been adjusted to the guidelines GLS formulated by the Ministry of Education and Culture.
Eve Eisenschmidt, Elina Kuusisto, Katrin Poom-Valickis & Kirsi Tirri (2019)	Virtues That Create Purpose For Ethical Leadership: Exemplary Principals From Estonia And Finland	Finland	Qualitative	-	Principals demonstrate the virtue of wisdom and knowledge in creating long-term provisions for their schools and building schools for future generations.
Gentari, Sumiati (2019)	The Influence Of Participatory Leadership Style and Motivation On The Employee's Spirit In The Departement Of Industry and Trade	Cilegon	Quantitative	50 employees	There is a significant influence of Participatory Leadership Style on the Employee's Work Spirit in the Department of Industry and Trade of the City of Cilegon.
Sumarsih (2017)	The Effect of Participatory Leadership and Learning Organizations on Performance with	Central Java	Quantitative	114	Showing participatory leadership has no effect on performance, participative leadership has no effect on psychological empowerment, psychological empowerment has a positive effect on performance, learning organization has an effect on performance, learning

	Psychological Empowerment as a Mediator in Junior High School Teachers in Central Java and DIY Provinces				organization has an effect on psychological empowerment.
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This section reports the main findings reviewed from several articles the author has read. Analysis shows that most articles focus on how participatory leadership practices are in schools. The article that has been reviewed is research conducted in Asia. Based on the articles reviewed, there are various ways of collecting data related to leadership in schools, the most commonly used is to use interviews and observation.

Research on participatory leadership practices in schools in Asia has been carried out in various countries. Table 1 shows that research has been carried out in schools, universities. The results of the majority of studies indicate that participatory leadership provides opportunities for subordinates to engage in institutional activities and the decision-making process for effective decision making in an institution must still receive the undue attention of a leader blaming the involvement of subordinates if he cannot make a decision effectively (Surasni, 2018). But in Felipe Aravena's research shows that Leaders have an impact on teacher perceptions about the leadership process (Aravena, 2019). In addition, the research conducted by Sumarseh showed that participatory leadership had no effect on performance, participative leadership had no effect on psychological empowerment, psychplogocal empowerment had a positive effect on performance, learning organization had an effect on performance, learning organization had an effect on psychological empowerment (Sumiarsih, 2017).

The principal always engages teachers in developing and implementing learning goals and objectives and the principal also refers to the curriculum set by the government in learning, participatory leadership can be a resource for teachers and staff, principals in implementing it always collaborate with teachers to improve learning programs in the classroom according to students' needs, then create learning development programs besides participatory leadership can communicate the vision and mission of the school to teachers and staff. The principal promotes and implements the contents and vision of the school well. The principal is able to establish habits of sharing opinions in determining the vision and mission of the school, and the school principal always maintains that the vision and mission of the school agreed upon by the school community is fertile in implementing it because the concept of instructional leadership focuses on teaching and learning activities and on the teacher's behavior in serving students. The participatory leadership model is usually interpreted as a school principal as a leader who in the process involves the active participation of various parties, both teachers, students, parents, students and all those related to improving the quality of learning in the educational institution.

The broad conclusion is when the writer considers all review of studies on participatory leadership practices in schools conducted in various countries in the world, shows that the leadership and leadership style of the principal is very important for an organization including educational institutions to have positive and negative impacts because of their academic influence in the field of education. As with research, this review has limitations. First, the articles are reviewed only in English so other studies are not reviewed because of limitations. Second, dissertations and these are not discussed in this article because they can cause publication bias in the results, Third, the scope of the article reviewed is still very limited, in this paper the scope is only limited to research conducted in Asian countries, while the variation of Asian countries reviewed is still lacking. A final limitation is that there is no single measure that can compare across studies.

V. CONCLUSION

Principal's leadership is very important for the success of school organizations because the leader creates positive changes in education by encouraging existing staff in the school to take initiative and change. The results of this literature indicate that the leadership and leadership style of the principal is very important for an organization including educational institutions to have a

positive and negative impact because it affects academics in the field of education due to leadership. Participatory is usually interpreted as a school principal as a leader who in the process involves the active participation of various parties, both teachers, students, parents, students and all those related to improving the quality of learning in educational institutions.

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